

Weight-Clustered Neural Networks for Low-Complexity Nonlinear Equalization in Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing Systems

Sasipim Srivallapanondh^{1*}, Pedro Freire¹, Giuseppe Parisi²,
Mariano Devigili³, Nelson Costa⁴, Bernhard Spinnler², Antonio Napoli²,
Jaroslaw E. Prilepsy¹ and Sergei K. Turitsyn¹

¹Aston University, Birmingham, UK; ²Infina, Munich, Germany;
³Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain; ⁴Infina, Carnaxide, Portugal
*s.srivallapanondh@aston.ac.uk

Abstract: We propose a low-complexity weight-clustered NN-based equalizer for digital subcarrier multiplexing systems. Our approach achieved a 91% complexity reduction compared to the perturbation-based model in previous literature and 93% relative to a non-clustered NN. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

In high-speed optical communications, addressing fiber nonlinearity is critical to achieve higher transmission rates and improved signal quality. Nonlinear effects, like the Kerr effect, limit the optical launch power and, consequently, the information rate in modern coherent systems, especially as symbol rate increases [1]. Various digital signal processing (DSP) techniques for nonlinear compensation, including digital back-propagation (DBP) [2], and Volterra-based equalizers [3], have been proposed, but their high computational complexity (CC) remains a challenge for real-time applications. Neural networks (NNs) have emerged as effective tools for optical channel equalization due to their ability to approximate the inverse channel transfer function and mitigate nonlinear distortions. They offer a potential reduction in CC compared to traditional methods [4]. Among NN architectures, recurrent NNs (RNNs), particularly long short-term memory (LSTM) modules, are more effective in handling nonlinear impairments in time-series data [5]. These NN architectures and the reduced-complexity NN models have been explored in single-carrier systems. However, few studies have focused on their use and their complexity in digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) systems [6, 7]. DSCM has recently emerged as an effective alternative to the single carrier systems to cope with rapid internet traffic evolution. This DSCM system is also promising for evolving optical networks from point-to-point to point-to-multipoint architectures, providing significant flexibility, and reducing capital and operational expenditures in optical networks [8]. In ref. [6], the authors have already proposed an NN architecture for DSCM systems. However, the CC of their approach is still relatively high.

This study explores the use of NN-based equalizers (NNE) in DSCM systems and applies weight clustering, a model compression technique that significantly reduces CC by minimizing the number of effective model weights [4]. The obtained results show that weight clustering enables up to 91% reduction in real multiplications per equalized symbols (RMpS) compared to the model based on perturbation coefficient in [6] and up to 93% decrease of RMpS compared to its uncompressed version while leading to just 0.35 dB Q-factor penalty.

2. Complexity Reduction of NNE with Weight Clustering

NNs have been widely studied for optical channel post-equalization due to their universal approximation capability. They have shown advantages over DBP regarding CC [4]. However, NN complexity remains a significant challenge for practical implementation, particularly in DSCM systems, where complexity reduction of NNE is still

Fig. 1: (a) Weight clustering framework and the weight distribution, showing the reduced number of unique weights after clustering; (b) biLSTM+1D-CNN-based NNE, recovering symbols of all four SCs simultaneously.

Fig. 2: Simulation setup of four SCs, total of 32 GBd, 16 QAM along 40×80 km SSMF or 15×80 km TWC.

underexplored. In this study, we reduce the CC of the NNE by using “Weight clustering”. The weight clustering method, also known as weight-sharing, is a model compression technique used in NNs to limit the number of unique weight values. This approach leverages the idea that many network connections can share the same value, thereby reducing the number of distinct multipliers needed for matrix multiplication. Shared weights are determined by clustering weights around centroids, forcing them to converge to the nearest centroid. Fig. 1a illustrates how the weight matrices are clustered into 3 weight clusters (WC) based on the centroids in the fully connected NN. The weight distributions of the NN without and with weight clustering are also presented in Fig. 1a, showing the significant reduction in the number of unique weights. As a result, the number of multiplications required in the NN is reduced, as multiple operations can be replaced by the additions and a single multiplication [4]. These shared weights can be fine-tuned to enhance accuracy. The NNE in this work consists of a bidirectional LSTM (biLSTM) module followed by a 1D-convolutional NN (CNN) layer, as shown in Fig. 1b. LSTM-based architectures have demonstrated superior performance in nonlinear compensation [5, 6]. Unlike RNNs, LSTMs capture long-term dependencies and overcome gradient issues [4]. The biLSTM module consists of forward and backward LSTM layers to retain information in both directions. In this model, the biLSTM module has 111 hidden units, and the 1D-CNN layer includes 8 filters with a kernel size of 15 and a linear activation function. The CNN recovers the real and imaginary parts of the X polarization for all subcarriers (SCs)¹. The input window has 221 symbols, with 16 input features representing real and imaginary parts of both polarizations of all four SCs. The model predicts 207 symbols per SC in each inference step. The loss function is MSE, and the optimizer is Adam with a learning rate of 5.81×10^{-4} . The training is carried out for 1000 epochs with a mini-batch size of 1742.

The numerical simulator² created the dataset by assuming a single-channel DSCM transmission with four SCs and dual polarization 16-QAM modulation format. The total symbol rate is 32 GBd, resulting in 8 GBd per SC. The transmission length is 40×80 km along standard single-mode fiber (SSMF) spans. At the transmitter side, the digital signals of each subcarrier are filtered by a digital root-raised cosine (RRC) filter with a 1/16 roll-off. At the end of each fiber span, optical fiber losses are compensated for by an EDFA with a 6 dB noise figure. The block diagram of the system is shown in Fig. 2. The SSMF is modeled with an effective nonlinearity coefficient $\gamma = 1.3 \text{ (W} \cdot \text{km)}^{-1}$, chromatic dispersion coefficient $D = 17 \text{ ps/(nm} \cdot \text{km)}$, and attenuation parameter $\alpha = 0.2 \text{ dB/km}$. Additionally, we have also considered transmission along TrueWave Classic (TWC) fiber with a total fiber length of 15×80 km and with the fiber parameters $\gamma = 2.5 \text{ (W} \cdot \text{km)}^{-1}$, $D = 2.8 \text{ ps/(nm} \cdot \text{km)}$, and $\alpha = 0.23 \text{ dB/km}$.

3. Results and Discussion

In the case of 40×80 km of SSMF, we compared our approach with previously published NN architecture in [6] called ‘M2 iSPM+iXPM’, which was trained based on perturbation coefficients. In this comparison, we referred to ‘M2 iSPM+iXPM-1’ as the model providing the best Q-factor and ‘M2 iSPM+iXPM-2’ as the reduced complexity version of the former model. Fig. 3a shows the Q-factor as a function of optical launch power for our original non-clustered NN, its compressed versions with 25, 35, and 45 WC; compared with CDC only, DBP with 1 STpS (steps per span), and the M2 iSPM+iXPM models [6]. As the number of WC decreases, performance declines. The NN with 45 WC experienced a Q-factor degradation of 0.1 dB compared to the original model, while the 35-WC NN showed a reduction of 0.17 dB, performing similarly to standard DBP with 1 STpS. The 25-WC NN showed a higher degradation of 0.35 dB, bringing the Q-factor down to 8.5 dB. Despite compression, all models maintained an optimal power level of 2 dBm. The performance of the original NN was comparable to the M2 iSPM+iXPM-1, while the NN with 25 WC matched the M2 iSPM+iXPM-2. We then compared the CC [4] of these approaches in terms of RMpS, see Fig. 3b. The results indicate that our NN with 25 WC achieved a 91.1% reduction in RMpS compared to Ref. [6]’s model with the lowest CC budget (M2 iSPM+iXPM-2), achieving a similar performance level. Specifically, M2 iSPM+iXPM-2 required 2.5×10^4 RMpS, while our NN with 25

¹ Simultaneous recovery of X and Y polarizations is possible but not tested here. Chromatic dispersion compensation (CDC) and NNE were applied separately to each polarization.

² Note that our simulator matched the optimum power and Q-factor of Ref. [6]. The performance in the nonlinear regime is nearly indistinguishable, whereas in the linear regime, our Q-factor was slightly better. However, our main focus here is the nonlinear regime.

Fig. 3: Q-factor VS launch power for the NNE and reduced complexity NNE compared to CDC and DBP for (a) 40×80 km of SSMF and (b) 15×80 km of TWC; CC in RMpS of different approaches in (c) SSMF and (d) TWC.

WC needed only 2215 RMpS. When evaluating models with higher Q-factor, our original NN allowed a 93.7% reduction in RMpS compared to the M2 iSPM+iXPM-1, with only a 0.1 dB degradation in Q-factor. The CC of DBP with 1 STpS and CDC are shown for reference.

Fig. 3c shows the Q-factor versus launch power for the original NN and the compressed models, with DBP with 1 STpS and CDC as baselines in the 15×80 km TWC system. The performance curves of the NN and its compressed versions exhibit a similar trend to the SSMF system, reflecting the trade-off between CC and performance. In this case, the optimal Q-factor for the original NN, and the NNs with 45 WC, 35 WC and 25 WC were 8.36, 8.20, 8.12 and 8.01 dB, respectively. The NNEs outperformed the DBP 1StpS which only compensated for self-phase modulation. Regarding CC, Fig. 3d shows the trade-off between performance and CC for all approaches. The original NN was the most computationally demanding, but yielded the highest Q-factor. With a 0.3 dB degradation in Q-factor, NN with 25 WC presented 92.9% less RMpS than the original NN.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that weight clustering can significantly reduce the computational complexity of neural network-based equalizers in DSCM systems while leading to minor Q-factor degradation only. The proposed approach effectively balances the trade-off between complexity and optical performance, offering reductions in real multiplications per equalized symbol (RMpS) of over 90% compared to the model based on perturbation analysis available in previous literature and our non-clustered NN, with minimal Q-factor degradation. These findings indicate that weight clustering is a promising method for implementing efficient nonlinear compensation in optical communications, paving the way for practical deployment in future high-speed networks.

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